

**APPLYING THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN OUR
COUNTRY OPPORTUNITIES.**

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Abstract: The article analyzes the experience of foreign countries in achieving sustainable development during the transition to a green economy and the use of effective methods in this direction in Uzbekistan. Scientifically based recommendations have been developed for the reorganization, reform and development of economic sectors in the regions of Uzbekistan with the aim of greening production.

Key words: ecological problem, green economy, foreign experience, environmental protection, sustainable development, region.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется опыт зарубежных стран по достижению устойчивого развития при переходе к зеленой экономике и использованию эффективных методов в этом направлении в Узбекистане. Разработаны научно обоснованные рекомендации по реорганизации, реформированию и развитию отраслей экономики в регионах Узбекистана с целью экологизации производства.

Ключевые слова: экологическая проблема, зеленая экономика, зарубежный опыт, охрана окружающей среды, устойчивое развитие, регион.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, humanity is experiencing important, decisive processes of problems related to environmental protection, problems related to ecology. If humanity does not take concrete and purposeful actions to eliminate the problems related to environmental protection, reduce their negative effects, and take measures that cause them to change in a positive direction, then every delayed the process has irreversible consequences. In other words, in short, now humanity is at a turning point in solving environmental problems, after this point, activities will have irreversible consequences, if from now

on we move towards specific goals, then we can achieve some positive results in this direction. can be entered into.

Due to the fact that the economic development models that have been in effect until now are based on the demand for resources and the development of labor demand, great damage has been done to the environment and nature. That is, the social effect of the produced products and services was lower than the social damage caused by damage to nature. Production in countries and regions was not minimized in terms of environmental risks.

The Covid-19 pandemic has shown that current economic models cannot solve the socio-economic problems facing the world economy. For this reason, the green economy model is considered the main factor in solving modern economic problems. Realizing this, many countries of the world are moving towards greening their economy. In Uzbekistan, environmental problems have been showing their negative effects on the efficiency of various sectors of the economy, on the health indicators of the population, and on the development levels of the regions. Environmentalization of regional economy and production is one of the important directions in solving these problems and reducing their impact. From this point of view, the development of scientific proposals and recommendations for the reorganization, formation, development of the economy of Uzbekistan and its regions from the point of view of green economy students, and their practical application are among the urgent and urgent issues of today.

In our country, the development of "green economy" is taking a leading place in ensuring sustainable development, rational use of limited, non-renewable economic resources, and increasing energy efficiency. It is important to study the scientific-theoretical and practical aspects of the formation of the "green economy", the laws of development, and its implementation in the transition of the national and regional economy to the path of innovative development.

LEVEL OF STUDY OF THE SUBJECT

In the economic literature, issues of green economy and ecologization of the economy have been studied since not so long ago. Annon (1996, 2001), Asafu-Adaye J. (2005), foreign scientists who conducted scientific research on the problems of economic greening. Biely K. (2014) Boulding

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M. M. Brinchuk, V. K. Donchenko, M. F. Zamyatina, M. N. Ignateva, N. N. Lukyanchikov, A. D. Malinin, Yu. V.

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N. F. Reimers, T. V. Rogova, A. S. Stepanovskikh, V. V. Haskin, S. V. Yakovlev, Ya. Yes. Yandiganov and others can be cited.

At the regional level, G. Ye. Mekush, A. M. Adam, M. V. Tereshina conducted research. In the works of V. I. Vernadsky, N. N. Moiseev, D. Kh. Meadows, N. F. Reimers, A. A. Grigorev, K. S. Losev, issues of modern principles of environmental policy are considered.

Acknowledging the great contribution of the above scientists to the development of science and the scientific field, we emphasize that in the conditions of Uzbekistan, especially in the economic development of its regions, taking into account the territorial characteristics of the region, in the elimination of environmental problems,

in the sustainable development of the economy, the issues of green economy its scientific and methodological foundations are not sufficiently developed, the modern development trends of its introduction have not been researched.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON MAZUG

A. V. Vahabov and Sh. In the article "Composition and development prospects of renewable energy consumption" by H. Hajibakiyev, the situation, composition and development prospects of renewable energy consumption were studied. The world experience of the development of "green energy" is comparatively analyzed and the possibilities of its use in Uzbekistan are described [1].

V. A. Pokhvoshev in his article "green economy" in the social development of Russia revealed the "green economy" and its role and importance in the social development of the Russian Federation. The authors analyzed the traditions of the formation of the green economy and its practical formation in Russia and the world experience, the development of prospects, the world and Russian experience of the network of environmental services and products [2].

M. M. Davletova in her research work entitled "Formation and development of the green economy in the conditions of the Central Asian region" presented the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the concept of green economy in the conditions of the Central Asian region, the main principles of its formation and development, issues of applying foreign experience in the Central Asian countries. conducted research on [3].

In the article by Y. A. Lyaskovskaya, K. M. Grigoreva, "Diagnostics of Territorial Possibilities of Transition to the Green Economy" Model, the main concept of green economy and green growth, the impact of green innovations and green economy on sustainable growth, and the experience of transition to green economy in foreign countries are analyzed. done [4].

A. M. Rodríguez, in the research work "Green economy in the context of sustainable growth problems", based on the mutual relations of the economy and the environment and their condition, the genesis of the green economy and its increasingly

acute environmental problems due to financial crises importance in elimination, ways to create new scientific approaches to greening the economy as a result of comprehensive research of the green economy and the environment, researched the importance of greening the economy in sustainable development [5].

V. Podgorniy, F. A. Shulenbayeva in the study entitled "Using the "green economic horse" in the sustainable development of Kazakhstan's agriculture" based on international programs on environmental protection and the study of agricultural land degradation international experience was studied, opportunities for the development of Kazakhstan's agriculture based on the principles of "green economy" were studied [7].

J. B. Smagulova, A. Y. Mukhanova, G. I. Musayevalar in the research work "Analysis of the world experience of the transition to the green economy: references and directions" the role of the green economy in the world economy, its development trends, the experience of the transition to the green economy from foreign countries and regions, the advantages and disadvantages of this experience are discussed [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Systematic analysis, statistical analysis, comparative comparison, synergistic analysis, interdisciplinary approach methods were used during the research. In particular, the method of systematic analysis was used in the analysis of literature and sources related to the topic, and the method of comparative analysis was used in the analysis of the experience of foreign countries.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Greening of the economy, development of the country's economy on the basis of the green economy, as a modern model of the economy, appeared in a relatively short period of time, but in a short period of time, it has become superior to the current models of the world economy in the period of global environmental and economic crises. is doing. Currently, economically developed countries are seeing the results of this in research and practice, so they are implementing it on a large scale in the economy and its various sectors, in different regions of the country. Investments in energy-efficient and natural infrastructure are already paying off.

Green economy is a new direction in the system of economic sciences that has appeared in the last 20-30 years, and its content explains the existence of the economy as a component of nature. The theory of green economy is based on three axioms, i.e. the impossibility of expanding the sphere of influence in a limited natural space, the impossibility of satisfying the endlessly growing desires in the conditions of limited resources, and the fact that everything on the surface of the Earth is interconnected. It is impossible to achieve constant economic growth, it is possible to achieve constant economic development.

Some economists argue that the current dominant economic systems are not perfect enough to respond to all aspects. Although these systems increase the economic and social well-being of some groups of countries and some strata of the population, it is clear that the damage they cause to the environment and nature is far greater than this benefit. In particular, widespread poverty in the regions, wastage of natural capital, lack of drinking water, food and energy, inequality between people and countries, and major environmental problems are among these.

Transition to green economy is required to eliminate these problems and promote the development of humanity. In different regions, different countries have started transitioning to the green economy on different scales and in different directions. Studying their experience in this regard, clarifying the positive trends in this direction, analyzing the negative consequences of the transition to a green economy, comparing the results, and researching the aspects of the countries' experience that are suitable for Uzbekistan are the goals of this research.

Green economy was adopted in 2008 as an idea of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP).[8].

It is necessary to harmonize the structural reforms implemented to reorient the world economy to a green economy as a sustainable model of social, economic and ecological growth. Experts recommend implementing reforms related to GDP growth and economic development through the introduction of the green economy in the following four directions.

First, the transition to a green economy is able to increase consumption resources of natural and human capital, that is, due to the effective management of natural capital and the increase of human potential, the state of the natural environment will improve, as a result of which the efficiency of using natural resources will increase.

Secondly, these changes, along with positive structural changes, require a large amount of investment in structural, basic sectors, including energy, construction, agriculture, household sector, etc. .

Thirdly, as an important factor in the development of the green economy, investments are allocated independently, mainly directed to sectors requiring alternative energy, such as the water supply system, sewage networks, and public transport.

Fourthly, the transition to a green economy stimulates innovative activities, as a result of which the competitive environment increases, innovative efficiency increases [10].

We will analyze the experience of some countries that have introduced the green economy as a priority.

South Korea is one of the leading countries in this field, which has introduced the green economy and is using it effectively. Since 2011, 3 percent of GDP in this country, that is, 60 bln. Funds in the amount of US dollars are directed to the development of the green sector. Over the past period, 1.8 million new jobs were created in this sector. Adopting the green economy as a national strategy, South Korea focuses on industry, energy, investment, green modes of transportation, alternative sources of drinking water, waste processing, development of recreational parks, and cleanliness of urban rivers. Various programs implemented by the ministries are combined into a single package in order not to overspend the budget. Since 2011, "green" payment cards have been introduced in South Korea in order to encourage the consumption of "green" goods and services.

Effective organization of alternative energy as a priority direction for the development of green economy in the USA began. A state program has been adopted

for this purpose, and it is planned to achieve 65% of the energy produced throughout the country with the help of solar panels in 2030. Since 2014, each state has adopted its own regional programs for the development of the green economy. For 10 years after 2016, investments are allocated on the basis of the program for the development of environmentally friendly technologies and the improvement of the environmental situation. Based on this program, it is planned to create 10 million new jobs.

Programs aimed at developing the green economy have been adopted in all EU member states. Energy, public transport and infrastructure, construction, waste disposal were selected as initial directions, and a large amount of work has been carried out so far.

In December 2019, the European Union adopted the "European Green Road" program. It is mainly aimed at achieving carbon neutrality in the region by 2050, reducing greenhouse gases by 55% compared to 1990 by 2030, investing in environmentally friendly technologies, using relatively clean and cheap types of public transport, encouraging industry to introduce innovations. Support, deurbanization of the energy sector, improvement of energy efficiency of buildings are planned.

In Europe, the Euro-6 standard for harmful gases emitted by cars has been adopted, and it is planned to introduce the Euro-7 standard in the European automobile industry from 2025. According to the Euro-7 standard, the production of cars with an internal combustion engine is prohibited.

In the field of introduction of green economy and its effective development in various sectors of the economy, China has achieved many results. The rapid growth of economic sectors, high population density, limited natural resources, and the emergence of a number of environmental problems require the transition of the Chinese economy to a green economy. China's initial emphasis on the transition to a green economy is to increase the use of renewable energy sources, increase the share of alternative energy in the country's energy balance, provide the population with clean drinking water and clean atmospheric air, as well as safe food products, and create an ecological culture. directed to take. In 2020, 15 percent of renewable energy is

renewable. In 2011-2015, more than 2 thousand ecologically harmful enterprises were compulsorily terminated.

China has been investing several times more in energy-efficient and renewable energy than the US and EU countries. As a result, in 2020, Chinese companies are exporting about 50 percent of the world's solar batteries and 25 percent of wind engines. Nowadays, a lot of attention is paid to nanotechnologies. At the beginning of 2022, the production of electric cars in the country increased by 45%, and now China has become the world leader in the production of electric cars, more than 60% of the electric cars of the world market are produced in this country. China plans to make its car fleet 100 percent green by 2035.

Uzbekistan has great opportunities to transition to a green economy. It is possible to indicate the natural and ecological conditions and resources of the region, indicators of the country's economic development, and available financial and economic resources. The natural and climatic conditions show that there is a huge reserve of alternative energy sources in the republic. High solar energy, developed industry, and the presence of large areas around residential areas increase the possibilities of using solar energy. Also, the presence of constant winds in the buffer zones of foothills and oasis and desert areas indicates the existence of wind energy opportunities [11].

In Uzbekistan, the initial processes of transition to a green economy have begun, legal frameworks are being formed in this regard, and a number of decrees and decisions have been formalized. In particular, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2019 "Approving the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2030" and the decree dated December 2, 2022 "2030 Among them are the decisions of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at transitioning to a "green" economy until 2008. Based on these legal and regulatory documents, it is intended to achieve the following strategic goals by 2030 [12].

- reducing greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product by 35% from the level of 2010;

- significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, introduce water-saving irrigation technology on an area of up to 1 million hectares;
- by planting 200 million saplings per year and increasing the total number of saplings from 1 billion, expanding green spaces in cities by more than 30 percent;
- increase the index of reserves of the republic's forest fund to more than 90 million cubic meters;
- increase the level of processing of generated solid household waste from 65 percent;
- Starting from June 1, 2023, introducing a system of "green certificates" based on the requirements for limiting the impact on ecology and the environment in the production of products;
- taking into account the emission of greenhouse gases by the state and maintaining their state cadastre;
- formation and maintenance of the register of carbon units;
- setting target indicators for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the sector of the economy;
- state support for activities to reduce greenhouse gas emissions;
- Establish a modern system of monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) in the field of climate change, covering all greenhouse gases from January 1, 2024;
- within the framework of the development of sector and regional development strategies, based on the characteristics of the sensitivity of sectors and regions to climate change, to reduce the impact of climate change on the population and economic sectors and to include measures and investment projects to adapt to it;
- Full implementation of the "polluter pays" principle by July 1, 2023;
- conducting fundamental and applied research on priority directions in the field of "green" economy;
- studying and putting into practice the possibilities of "green" technologies in economic sectors, in particular, resource-saving, zero-waste production, transition to

the use of technologies that enable waste processing and safe chemicals, and the use of renewable energy technologies ;

- measures such as the implementation of promising innovative developments and "startup" projects and their commercialization and support for technology transfer are planned.

The author is the introduction and development of the green economy in the conditions of Uzbekistan at the present time, in the initial period

recommends the following as directions:

- In the field of waste disposal. In this sector, it is necessary to quickly introduce the principles of green economy. This, in turn, reduces the problems of environmental pollution, and also leads to the reduction of problems related to human health;

- In the field of use of natural resources (land, water, biological, atmosphere). It is necessary to increase the efficiency of natural resources use, to introduce resource-efficient technologies. In this, the issues of food and water safety, production of ecologically pure products will also be partially solved;

- In the field of energy. As a solution to problems such as the energy crisis observed in the country in the winter season of 2022-2023, it is necessary to increase alternative energy sources in the regions of the country, to modernize the existing energy capacities;

- In the field of agriculture and water economy production. Modernization of production technologies in agriculture, modernization of production capacities, increase of the efficiency of hydrotechnical facilities will lead to a large amount of resource saving in the field;

- In the field of public and private transport. Greening of the transport system is a solution to atmospheric air issues, and it also forms a saving in energy consumption;

- It is necessary to strengthen the financing of green technologies and green production processes, to introduce a system of incentives for the introduction of such technologies;

■ In the field of strengthening ecological culture. It is necessary to increase awareness of the attitude to nature, environmental protection among the participants of different strata of society, to strengthen propaganda about the effectiveness of modern resource-efficient technologies and ecological culture.

XULOSA AND OFFERS

World experience shows that the green economy, along with ensuring regional and macroeconomic development, leads to an increase in the well-being of the population, improvement of the natural environment and public health. It is known from the experience of developed countries that in the initial development of the green economy, it is effective to focus on the priority sectors and to expand their capabilities, while greening other sectors of the economy as well.

Uzbekistan has sufficient natural-climatic, ecological, financial-economic, and technological opportunities for the transition to a green economy and its effective development. In this regard, the experience of leading foreign countries is used.

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